

1 **Long-term validation of polyhydroxyalkanoates production potential from the sidestream of municipal**
2 **wastewater treatment plant at pilot scale**

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14 **Keywords**

15 Anaerobic Digestion; Volatile Fatty Acids; Water Resource Recovery Facilities; Nitrogen removal; Bioplastics

16 *Abbreviations:* AD, anaerobic digestion; AOB, ammonium oxidizing bacteria; A-SBR, accumulation SBR; AUR,

17 ammonium utilization rate; CH₄, methane; COD, chemical oxygen demand; COD_{SOL}, soluble COD; CPS,

18 cellulosic primary sludge; CPSFL, cellulosic primary sludge fermentation liquid; DO, dissolved oxygen; FA,

19 free ammonia; HRT, hydraulic retention time; MLVSS, mixed liquor volatile suspended solids; MMCs, mixed

20 microbial cultures; NAR, nitrite accumulation rate; NH₄-N, nitrogen as ammonia; NO₂-N, nitrogen as nitrite;

21 NOB, nitrite oxidizing bacteria; NO_x-N, nitrogen as nitrite and nitrate; N-SBR, nitrification SBR; OM, organic

22 matter; ORP, oxydation reduction potential; PE, population equivalent; PHA, polyhydroxyalkanoates; PO₄-P,

23 phosphorus as phosphate; RBDF, rotating belt dynamic filter; S/L, solid/liquid separation; SBFR, sequencing

24 batch fermentation reactor; SBR, sequencing batch reactor; SRT, solid retention time; S-SBR, selection SBR;

25 TKN, total kjeldahl nitrogen; TP, total phosphorus; TSS, total suspended solids; TVS, total volatile solids; UF,
26 ultrafiltration; VFAs, volatile fatty acids; vNLR, volumetric nitrogen loading rate; vOLR, volumetric organic
27 loading rate; VSS, volatile suspended solids; WAS, waste activated sludge; WRRF, water resource recovery
28 facility; WW, wastewater; WWTP, wastewater treatment plant; Xa, active biomass

29

30 **Abstract**

31 In this study, polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) production integrated with the via-nitrite nitrogen removal
32 from anaerobic reject water was investigated at pilot scale under long term period. The pilot plant was
33 located in Carbonera wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) (Treviso, Italy) and comprised the following
34 units: i) rotating belt dynamic filter (RBDF) for the recovery of cellulosic primary sludge (CPS); ii)
35 fermentation unit for the production of volatile fatty acids (VFAs); iii) ultrafiltration unit (UF) for solid/liquid
36 separation of the fermented sludge; iv) nitrification sequencing batch reactor (N-SBR) for the oxidation of
37 ammonia to nitrite; v) selection SBR (S-SBR) where aerobic-feast and anoxic-famine conditions were
38 established to select PHA-accumulating biomass and vi) an accumulation SBR (A-SBR) where intracellular
39 PHA content was maximized through the feed-on-demand strategy. Results showed that around 80% of the
40 influent ammonia was efficiently removed by the system when both N-SBR and S-SBR operated with
41 volumetric nitrogen loading rate (vNLR) of 1.64-1.72 kgN/m³ d and 0.60-0.63 kgN/m³ d. Accumulation tests
42 showed PHA yields ranging between 0.58 and 0.61 g COD_{PHA}/g COD_{VFA}, indicating an effective selection
43 strategy. The overall mass balance assessment demonstrated that around 0.32 grams of COD per gram of
44 COD treated can be recovered as bio-based products. The integration of nitrogen removal and PHA
45 production in the sidestream resulted in a methane recovery up to 4.0 m³CH₄/PE y and a maximal PHA
46 production of 1.2 kgPHA/PE y with a potential revenue for the WWTP up to 6.5 €/PE y.

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50 **1. Introduction**

51 Over the last decades, a lot of efforts have been directed to change the paradigm of WWTPs from an end-
52 of-pipe infrastructure to WRRFs. In this new paradigm, wastewater (WW) is considered as a renewable
53 resource from which water, energy and materials can be recovered [1]. Biogas production has been widely
54 adopted to partially offset the energy consumption for wastewater treatment [2]. However, the low value
55 and energy content of the CH₄ has led to the development of new technologies aiming at the upgrade of
56 the OM to a higher value bioproducts [3]. In recent years, great interest has been given to PHAs production
57 due to their wide application as environmental-friendly bioplastics [4]. These biopolymers are completely
58 biodegradable and produced by over 300 bacterial species as carbon and energy reserve [5]. Their
59 biosynthesis is usually stimulated by the presence of excess carbon in concomitance with the absence of
60 macronutrients (i.e. nitrogen or phosphorus) or transient excess of soluble carbon without any nutrient
61 limitation (i.e. feast/famine environment [6]). Commercial PHAs production currently uses expensive
62 sources of OM and pure bacterial consortium, increasing the production costs from around two to five
63 times in comparison with fossil-fuel based plastics [7]. In 2014, the PHA market price varied between 4 and
64 5 €/kg from the high-value medical product to low-value consumables for agricultural purpose [8]. A recent
65 forecast of the European Bioplastics Association [9] showed an increase of the PHA production capacity up
66 to 6 times more by 2024. To fill this gap, the use of open mixed- instead of pure-cultures and low-cost
67 carbon sources could be considered a valid alternative due to the large interest gained over the last years.
68 The typical process for MMCs PHAs production usually comprises three different steps: i) acidogenic
69 fermentation VFAs production, ii) selection of biomass with significant PHA production capability and iii)
70 accumulation to maximize the intracellular PHA content. Nevertheless, although fundamentals and
71 methods for PHA production from MMCs have been largely published in literature, the technology
72 readiness level (TRL) still remains low (i.e. <5 [3]). Moreover, a suitable PHA extraction and purification
73 process has not been identified yet although several techniques were investigated in literature [7,10]. The
74 type of recovery technique has to be selected according to the desired properties and purity which will also
75 affect the selling price in the market.

76 To date, few studies on MMC-PHAs production at pilot scale from different feedstocks have been reported
77 in literature. Anterrieu et al. [11] investigated the integration of PHAs production with wastewater
78 treatment in a Dutch sugar factory, while Valentino et al. [12] described a biorefinery for the conversion of
79 the organic fraction of municipal solid waste (OFMSW) and WAS into PHAs. In another work, Bengtsson et
80 al. [13] studied the feasibility of PHAs production from municipal wastewater treatment with biological
81 carbon and nitrogen removal. In this study, the carbon source for PHAs production was obtained from the
82 acidogenic fermentation of an agro-industrial residual feedstock coming from local green-house tomato
83 production. However, in all of these works, industrial and/or non-municipal organic contributions were
84 evaluated, hindering the assessment of the actual PHA production potential from sole municipal
85 wastewater. On the other hand, Morgan-Sagastume et al. [14] investigated the integrated municipal
86 wastewater and sludge treatment with PHA production. The authors applied a feast/famine process in a
87 pilot-scale SBR where the carbon source for the selection of PHA-accumulating biomass consisted of readily
88 biodegradable soluble carbon present in raw WW. In the same study seasonal variability of WW
89 characteristics were found, which implies a possible disadvantageous process instability from an industrial
90 perspective. Based on previous pilot-scale results, Morgan-Sagastume et al. [15] reported the first techno-
91 environmental assessment for the integration of PHA production with municipal WW treatment. The
92 authors considered four different WWTP scenarios for carbon source production and biological nutrients
93 removal. The results showed that the overall organic carbon conversion in WWTPs (0.26 gCOD/gCOD
94 treated) was the same when AD was applied by itself or in combination with PHAs production. However,
95 parameters for process design and estimation of potential PHA production from municipal wastewater
96 itself have not been reported yet.

97 To boost the driver for conversion of WWTPs into WRRFs, an integrated PHA recovery via-nitrite from the
98 sidestream treatment in WWTPs has been proposed by Frison et al. [16]. Coupling PHAs production within
99 the treatment of more concentrate streams could represents a suitable option, since it decreases: i)
100 volumes that needs to be managed; ii) costs for nutrients removal in the main line and iii) it ensures higher
101 process stability due to the more stationary characteristics of these sidestream flows. The importance of

102 optimizing the fermentation yields for VFAs production is crucial to increase the sustainability of the
103 process. Lee et al. [17] reported yields between 85 and 300 mgCOD_{VFA}/gVSS when sole primary sludge was
104 fermented. Crutchik et al. [18] investigated the use of CPS to maximize carbon diversion and its further
105 valorization through VFAs production. Highest VFAs yield of 340mgCOD_{VFA}/gTVS_{fed} has been found,
106 underlining the potential of this substrate for on-site carbon source production. More recently, the use of
107 CPS for several purposes, including VFAs production, has been investigated at pilot scale by Da Ros et al.
108 [19]. Fermentation yields up to 322mgCOD_{VFA}/gTVS_{fed} in a sequencing batch fermentation reactor were
109 reported, and different scenarios for CPS valorization were considered. The authors found that upgrading
110 VFAs derived from CPS into high added value products such as PHAs would significantly increase the
111 revenue of WWTPs, highlighting the importance of carbon diversion towards the development of WRRFs.
112 The present study is aimed to validate the long-term operation of an innovative pilot-scale plant integrating
113 via-nitrite nitrogen removal with PHAs production from the sidestream of Carbonera WWTP (Treviso, Italy).
114 A novel substrate derived from fermentation of CPS was used as carbon source to evaluate the impacts on
115 PHAs production. Each process unit was investigated to assess the long-term stability of the process and to
116 define the parameters required for the full-scale implementation. Moreover, the overall mass balance was
117 accomplished to answer to the following question: what is the actual PHAs production potential from sole
118 municipal wastewater in the sidestream of WWTPs?

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120 **2. Materials and methods**

121 2.1 Carbonera WWTP

122 The pilot plant was located inside of the Carbonera WWTP (Treviso, northern Italy). The full-scale plant had
123 a treatment capacity of 40,000 PE and treated around 15,000 m³/day of municipal wastewater without any
124 industrial contribution. The water line was composed by preliminary treatments, primary sedimentation,
125 biological reactor (Schreiber process), secondary sedimentation, disinfection and final filtration. The sludge
126 line was composed by a static pre-thickener followed by dynamic thickening (installed during the
127 experimental period) of mixed primary and secondary sludge, equalization tank for thickened sludge,

128 anaerobic digester and the Short-Cut Enhanced Nutrients Abatement (S.C.E.N.A.) system for the treatment
129 of sludge reject water [20].

130 2.2 Process units and flowchart

131 The pilot plant treated around 10% (1.5-3.0 m³/day) of the daily anaerobic reject water produced, while the
132 system comprised of six different units, as reported below:

133 1) RBDF for the recovery of CPS; 2) SBFR for the production of VFAs by acidogenic fermentation; 3) UF unit
134 for S/L; 4) N-SBR; 5) S-SBR; 6) Fed-batch accumulation reactor (A-SBR).

135 The flowchart of the process is reported in Figure 1.

136

137 Figure 1. Schematic representation of the pilot plant

138 The scheme reported above was adapted from a previous study [16], in which the carbon source (VFAs)
139 were produced by the acidogenic fermentation of mixed primary and secondary sludge instead of CPS from
140 wastewater sieving as in this work.

141 2.3 Characteristics of the anaerobic reject water

142 The whole experiment lasted more than 600 days and three different experimental periods were identified
143 on the basis of both the characteristics of the anaerobic reject water and the operating conditions of the
144 system. Period 1 was between days 1-84, period 2 between days 170-319 while period 3 between days 370-
145 613. On the other hand, characteristics of the anaerobic reject water has been mainly affected in period 2

146 and 3 by the implementation of the dynamic thickening of the sewage sludge. The latter increased the
 147 suspended solids concentration of the sewage sludge from 2.5% up to 5.0% on dry matter. The complete
 148 characteristics of the anaerobic reject water were reported in the Table 1.

149 Table 1. Characteristics of the reject water during the different periods

Parameter	Unit	Period 1	Period 2	Period 3
		(days 1-84) Average±st.dev	(days 170-319) Average±st.dev	(days 379-613) Average±st.dev
Dynamic thickening of sewage sludge	-	NO	YES	YES
COD	mgCOD/L	284±104	1855±713	1116±303
COD _{SOL}	mgCOD/L	56±11	1613±620	970±224
VFAs	mgCOD/L	ND	547±149	64±14
TKN	mgN/L	449±34	1300±168	1187±119
NH ₄ -N	mgN/L	401±31	1161±150	1060±106
TP	mgP/L	24.9±3.8	25.2±4.0	27.8±8.3
PO ₄ -P	mgP/L	23.0±3.1	23.3±3.7	25.7±7.7

150

151 2.4 SBFR for VFAs production from CPS

152 The SBFR (TA, Italy) was composed by a stainless-steel tank (AISI 304) with a total volume of 3.0 m³. The
 153 working volume was kept at 2.6 m³ and the temperature was maintained at 37°C by an electrical heating
 154 system with an installed power of 1.5 kW. CPS was recovered through a RBDF (SF1000, Salsnes Filter,
 155 Norway) which operated with a mesh size of 350 µm in both period 1 and 2, while in period 3 a mesh size of
 156 210 µm was installed. The operating mechanism of the RBDF is described in Franchi and Santoro (2015).
 157 The HRT of the fermenter varied between 4 and 6 days, pH was not controlled while the mixed liquor was
 158 kept under continuous agitation by a mixer (Motovario TH80B4, Italy) at 20 rpm. Before entering the UF
 159 unit, the fermented sludge was screened by a basket filter (SATI filter, Cesena, Italy) with a porosity of 3
 160 mm and a volume of 5 L. The fermented cellulosic primary sludge was filtered by the S/L unit which was
 161 constituted by seven ceramic membranes, each one with 8 tubular channels with a porosity of 0.2 µm and a
 162 specific surface area of 0.2 m² (Septra, Cesano Maderno, Italy). The membranes operated with an internal
 163 recycle flowrate of 30-35 m³/h and the working pressure ranged from 3.5-4 bar and 1.5-2 bar in the inlet

164 and effluent part of the membrane, respectively, resulting in flux of around 100 L/m² h of permeate that
 165 was then stored in a tank with a volume of 1 m³. The characteristics of CPSFL are reported below.

166 Table 2. Characteristics of the CPSFL during the experimental periods

Parameter	Unit	Period 1 and 2	Period 3
		Average±st.dev	Average±st.dev
pH	-	4.8±0.1	4.9±0.2
COD _{SOL}	mgCOD/L	8786±1568	12830±1529
VFAs	mgCOD/L	8347±1754	9975±1984
Acetic Acid	mgCOD/L	2086±317	2892±301
Propionic Acid	mgCOD/L	4424±356	5087±428
Butyric Acid	mgCOD/L	1042±237	1273±185
Valeric Acid	mgCOD/L	795±55	723±89
COD _{VFA} /COD _{SOL}	%	86±3	77±6
C ₃ /(C ₂ +C ₃)*	mol/mol	0.52±0.06	0.49±0.08
NH ₄ -N	mgN/L	326±23	290±19
PO ₄ -P	mgN/L	70±12	72±15

167 *C2: VFAs species with even number of carbons; C3: VFAs species with odd number of carbons

168 2.5 Nitritation SBR

169 The N-SBR consisted in a stainless-steel SBR with a working volume of 1.1 m³. The operating cycle was
 170 composed by the following phases: idle, feeding, aerobic, settling and discharge. The SBR was inoculated by
 171 taking the sludge from the biological reactor of the main wastewater treatment line and the adopted
 172 strategy for AOB enrichment was to maintain a level of FA always higher than 1.5 mg NH₃/L to foster the
 173 nitrite oxidizing bacteria (NOB) washout [21]. The anaerobic reject water was pumped from an equalization
 174 tank (90 m³) through a volumetric pump (Sydex, Lonigo, Italy) with a flowrate of 3.6 m³/h, while the
 175 effluent was withdrawn through a centrifuge pump (Lowara, Milan, Italy) with a flowrate of 6 m³/h in an
 176 equalization tank with a volume of 1.4 m³. The reactor was equipped with probes (Hach-Lange, Germany)
 177 for the monitoring of the process, in particular conductivity, pH and dissolved oxygen (DO). Four ultra-fine
 178 bubble diffusers (INVENT, USA) were placed at the bottom of the reactor and oxygen was provided through
 179 a centrifuge blower (Mapro, Vicenza, Italy) with a flowrate of 17-20 m³/h and controlled at 1.5 ± 0.5 mg

180 O₂/L through a manual valve installed on the pipe for air supply. pH was controlled at 7.5-8.0 by automatic
 181 addition of 30% NaOH (w/v) through a peristaltic pump. Temperature was not controlled during the first
 182 part of the experimental period, while a heating system was installed after period 1. Steady state
 183 conditions were considered when the NAR (eq. 1) was >95% for approximately 3 x solids retention time
 184 (SRT).

185
$$\text{NAR (\%)} = \frac{\text{NO}_2^-}{\text{NO}_2^- + \text{NO}_3^-} \times 100 \quad \text{eq.1}$$

186 In Table 3 the operating conditions of N-SBR among the different periods under steady-state conditions are
 187 reported.

188 Table 3. Operating conditions of the N-SBR

Parameter	Unit	Period 1*	Period 2	Period 3
		Average±st.dev	Average±st.dev	Average±st.dev
Heated	-	NO	YES	YES
Temperature	°C	18.9±2.1	26.6±1.4	25.5±1.7
SRT	day	13-15	22-25	22-25
HRT	day	0.99±0.2	0.82±0.16	0.73±0.13
vNLR	kgN/m ³ day	0.64±0.35	1.60±0.26	1.62±0.25
vOLR	kgCOD/m ³ day	0.06±0.01	1.78±0.11	0.68±0.05
Cycles	n°/day	5.0±1.2	4.5±0.2	4.8±0.2

189 *Only pseudo steady-state conditions were achieved (days 10-47)

190 2.6 Selection SBR

191 The S-SBR consisted in a stainless-steel SBR with a total volume of 2.8 m³ and operated under (aerobic)-
 192 feast and (anoxic)-famine conditions. The operating cycle was composed by four different phases that
 193 occurred as follow: idle, feast, famine, settling and discharge. The selection strategy for the start-up was to
 194 apply a feast/famine ratio lower than 0.2 min/min, since this had been reported as a limit value to sustain a
 195 microbial consortium that will accomplish excess PHAs storage over growth [22,23]. The seed sludge was
 196 the same as for the N-SBR. Oxygen was provided during feast conditions by a centrifuge blower (Mapro,
 197 Vicenza, Italy) and ten ultrafine bubbles diffusers (INVENT, USA) placed in the bottom of the tank. Two

198 probes (Hach-Lange, Germany) were installed within the reactor for the monitoring of ORP and DO. The
 199 blower was controlled by a variable frequency drive (VFD) to maintain a DO concentration of 2 ± 0.2
 200 mgO_2/L , resulting in a flowrate between 25-60 m^3/h . The bulk liquid was mixed under anoxic conditions
 201 through a mixer (Motovario TH80B4, Modena, Italy) with a speed of 100 rpm. At the beginning of the cycle
 202 (feast phase), the carbon source was fed through a centrifuge pump (Lowara, Milan, Italy) with a flowrate
 203 of 6 m^3/h , while the effluent from N-SBR was pumped from the equalization tank to the S-SBR through a
 204 centrifuge pump (Lowara, Milan, Italy) with a flowrate of 6 m^3/h as soon as the famine phase started. In this
 205 way, nitrite was used as electron acceptor for biomass growth [16] during the denitrification. The treated
 206 effluent from S-SBR was finally discharged at the end of the cycle by a pneumatic valve. Steady state
 207 conditions were considered when the length of the feast phase remained constant for at least for 3 x SRT.
 208 The operating conditions of the S-SBR during the different periods are reported in Table 4.

209 Table 4. Operating conditions of the S-SBR

Parameter	Unit	Period 1*	Period 2	Period 3
		Average $\pm$ st.dev	Average $\pm$ st.dev	Average $\pm$ st.dev
Heated	-	NO	YES	YES
Temperature	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	18.8 $\pm$ 2.1	25.4 $\pm$ 1.4	26.8 $\pm$ 1.7
SRT	day	6-7	6-7	6-7
HRT	day	2.3 $\pm$ 0.6	2.0 $\pm$ 0.2	1.7 $\pm$ 0.2
tot vNLR	$\text{kgN}/\text{m}^3 \text{d}$	0.18 $\pm$ 0.05	0.60 $\pm$ 0.14	0.63 $\pm$ 0.12
vNO ₂ -NLR	$\text{kgN}/\text{m}^3 \text{d}$	0.05 $\pm$ 0.03	0.47 $\pm$ 0.12	0.49 $\pm$ 0.11
vNO _x -NLR	$\text{kgN}/\text{m}^3 \text{d}$	0.14 $\pm$ 0.01	0.48 $\pm$ 0.12	0.50 $\pm$ 0.11
vOLR	$\text{kgCOD}/\text{m}^3 \text{d}$	0.89 $\pm$ 0.11	1.31 $\pm$ 0.07	1.58 $\pm$ 0.10
vOLR _{VFA}	$\text{kgCOD}_{\text{VFA}}/\text{m}^3 \text{d}$	0.77 $\pm$ 0.12	1.15 $\pm$ 0.07	1.22 $\pm$ 0.11
COD _{SOL} /NO _x -N	kgCOD/kgN	6.36 $\pm$ 2.4	2.73 $\pm$ 0.21	3.17 $\pm$ 0.24
COD _{VFA} /NO _x -N	kgCOD/kgN	5.51 $\pm$ 2.3	2.41 $\pm$ 0.18	2.49 $\pm$ 0.22
Cycles	n $^{\circ}$ /d	2.1 $\pm$ 0.6	2.5 $\pm$ 0.6	2.7 $\pm$ 0.3

210 * Only pseudo steady-state conditions were achieved

211 2.7 PHA accumulation tests

212 The maximum accumulation potential of the biomass was evaluated by several accumulation batches fed
213 according with a multiple pulse-feeding strategy [12]. The accumulation reactor (A-SBR) consisted in a
214 stainless-steel tank with a volume of 1 m³ which operated as a fed-batch reactor. The reactor was equipped
215 with a DO probe (Hach-Lange, Germany) and three ultra-fine bubble diffusers (INVENT, USA) placed at the
216 bottom of the tank which provided oxygen through a centrifuge blower (Mapro, Vicenza, Italy) with a
217 flowrate of 17 m³/h. The excess sludge from the S-SBR was transferred to the A-SBR at the end of the cycle.
218 The accumulation trials lasted between 6-7 h and the carbon source was added based on feed-on-demand
219 strategy using DO as control parameter [24], according with an initial COD concentration of around 0.7-1.2
220 g COD_{VFA}/L to prevent any substrate inhibition as reported by Valentino et al. [12].

221 2.8 Analytical methods and online measurements

222 All the signals from the different units were continuously recorded and stored in a Programmable Logic
223 Controller (PLC, S7-1200, Siemens, USA) which also controlled the whole operation of the system.

224 Analytical samples were taken daily from both the N-SBR and S-SBR and only during the accumulation tests
225 in the A-SBR. TSS and VSS, COD, COD_{SOL}, TKN and TP were determined according to standard methods
226 [25,26]. Nitrites, nitrates and phosphates were determined by high performance ion chromatography
227 (Dionex ICS-900 with AG14 column and AMMS 300 suppressor) on filtered samples (0.2 μm, Whatman
228 syringe filters). VFAs were determined through an Agilent 6890N gas chromatograph (GC) equipped with a
229 flame ionization detector (FID) with a temperature of 230°C and an Agilent J&W DB-FFAP fused silica
230 capillary column (15m x 0.53mm x 0.5mm) using hydrogen as gas carrier. The instrument operated with a
231 ramp temperature from 80 to 200°C using 2-ethylbutyric acid as internal standard. Samples were prepared
232 before GC analysis through filtration (0.2 μm, Whatman syringe filters) and acidification at pH 2 with
233 orthophosphoric acid. The quantification of each carboxylic acid was carried using a calibration curve built
234 using the analytical standard Volatile free Acid Mix (Merck KGaA, Germany).

235 For PHA quantification, each sludge sample (5.0 mL) was pre-treated with a sodium hypochlorite solution
236 (1.0 mL; 5% active chlorine) and placed in a freezer at -20°C. The PHA quantification was carried out by
237 using a gas chromatographic method, based on the acid methanolysis with acidified methanol (3% v/v

238 H₂SO₄). The acidic hydrolysis of PHA followed by the methyl derivatization reaction generated volatile
239 monomers, the methyl esters of 3-hydroxybutyric (3HB) and 3-hydroxyvaleric (3HV) acids.
240 The sample preparation procedure involved a thawing, centrifugation (8.500 rpm, 20 min) removal of the
241 supernatant and quantitative transfer of the solid residue into pyrex glass tubes with 2.0 mL of the acidified
242 methanol solution containing benzoic acid (0.05 g/L) as an internal standard. Then, 1.0 mL of CHCl₃ was
243 added and the whole was digested for 4 hours at 100°C. After cooling, the addition of 1.0 mL of distilled
244 water and the mixing generated two separate aqueous and organic phases. For the analysis, 1.0 µL of
245 organic phase was injected into the gas chromatograph based on the method illustrated in [27].
246 The abundance of 3HB-3HV monomers were quantified using P(3HB-co-3HV) Sigma-Aldrich standard
247 polymer at 5 wt % HV content.

248

249 2.9 Calculations

250 Nitrogen mass balances were calculated according to Battistoni et al. [28], while FA at different
251 temperatures was calculated according to Anthonisen et al. [21]. For the calculation of Ammonia Utilization
252 Rate (AUR, mg N/L h), ammonia profile was plotted over time using a linear regression analysis. The specific
253 AUR (mg N/g VSS h) was calculated by normalizing the AUR for the X_a concentration (VSS in the case of N-
254 SBR). In this study, VFAs were expressed as mg COD/L and were considered as the sum of the different
255 species as reported by Frison et al [16]. The feast/famine ratio was calculated as the ratio between the
256 length of the feast phase and the length of the famine phase, according to the following equation (eq.2):

$$257 \text{ Feast/Famine (min/min)} = \frac{t_{\text{Feast}}}{t_{\text{Famine}}} \quad \text{eq.2}$$

258 Where t famine is considered the period (aerobic and/or anoxic conditions) of the cycle between the
259 complete depletion of the VFAs and end anoxic phase. PHA concentration was converted into COD
260 according to the following oxidation stoichiometry: 1.67 g COD/g HB and 1.92 g COD/g HV. The total
261 concentration was calculated as the sum of PHB and PHV (eq.3):

$$262 \text{ PHA (mgCOD/L)} = \sum (\text{PHB} + \text{PHV}) \quad \text{eq.3}$$

263 The PHA content within the biomass was expressed considering the equation:

$$264 \quad \text{PHA (\%)} = \frac{\text{g}^{\text{PHA}}}{\text{g}^{\text{VSS}}} \times 100 \quad \text{eq.4}$$

265 The concentration of X_a in both S-SBR and A-SBR was calculated by subtracting the concentration of PHA
266 (g/L) from the concentration of VSS (g/L). X_a was then converted into COD by the stoichiometric value of
267 1.42 g COD/g X_a as reported by Tchobanoglous et al. [29].

268 The VFAs utilization rate (-qVFA, mg COD/g X_a h), was calculated by dividing the concentration of VFAs
269 consumed with the duration of the feast phase. PHA storage yield (Y_{PHA/VFA}, g COD_{PHA}/g COD_{VFA}) and growth
270 yield (Y_{X/VFA}, g X_a/g COD_{VFA}) were determined according to the following equations (eq.5 and eq.6):

$$271 \quad Y_{\text{PHA/VFA}} = \frac{\text{gCOD}_{\text{PHA}} \text{ produced}}{\text{gCOD}_{\text{VFA}} \text{ consumed}} \quad \text{eq.5}$$

$$272 \quad Y_{\text{X/VFA}} = \frac{\text{VSS-PHA (g/L)}}{\text{COD}_{\text{VFA}} \text{ consumed (g/L)}} \quad \text{eq.6}$$

273 **3. Results and discussion**

274 3.1 Performances of the nitrification SBR

275 The reactor was operated for more than 600 days globally. In order to accomplish a proper selection of the
276 PHA-accumulating biomass, an adequate amount of electron acceptor (nitrite in this work) should be
277 provided in the S-SBR. In the specific case, the design parameters of the N-SBR considered a daily
278 production in the range of 1.2-1.5 kg NO_x-N/d with a nitrification efficiency of about 85% and a NAR higher
279 than 95%, resulting in a vNO₂-NLR in the selection stage of 0.4-0.6 kg NO₂-N/m³ d and residual ammonia to
280 favor the growth of the PHA-biomass. The nitrite load in the S-SBR derived from a previous study conducted
281 by Frison et al. [16], in which a similar nitrite loading in a lab-scale reactor with a comparable configuration
282 to the present work was applied. The table below resumes nitrogen mass balances and oxidation
283 efficiencies of N-SBR.

284 Table 5. Nitrogen mass balances and oxidation efficiencies of the N-SBR

Parameter	Unit	Period 1	Period 2	Period 3
		Average (Min-Max)	Average (Min-Max)	Average (Min-Max)
tot NLR in	kg N/d	0.69 (0.21-1.39)	1.80 (1.02-2.29)	1.89 (1.21-2.73)
NH ₄ -NLR in	kg N/d	0.63 (0.15-1.31)	1.64 (0.95-2.07)	1.72 (1.06-2.54)
NH ₄ -NLR out	kg N/d	0.12 (0.01-1.12)	0.18 (0.01-0.71)	0.30 (0.02-0.61)
NO ₂ -NLR out	kg N/d	0.16 (0.03-0.58)	1.31 (0.64-1.52)	1.35 (0.77-1.80)
NO _x -NLR out	kg N/d	0.49 (0.10-1.10)	1.33 (0.65-1.59)	1.36 (0.77-1.83)
X-NLR out	g N/d	9.8 (9.1-11.3)	16.7 (13.2-23.4)	10.4 (7.8-11.9)
Ammonia oxidation efficiency				
Nitrification Eff	%	81.6 (70.0-99.5)	88.9 (45.0-99.5)	82.5 (62.9-98.8)
NAR	%	32.6 (4.6-52.7)	98.5 (94.7-99.8)	99.2 (97.6-99.9)

285 As shown above, the amount of nitrite produced was different among the different periods. Indeed, after
286 the start-up in period 1, the combination of shorter SRT and low temperature resulted in the production of
287 only 0.16 kgNO₂-N/d, which was quite lower production compared to the demands of the S-SBR. In period
288 1, although the nitrification efficiency was about 81.6% (Table 5) the NAR was only 32.6%, indicating a not
289 established a complete via-nitrite pathway. However, the daily amount of produced NO_x was about 0.49
290 kgNO_x-N/d. The low NAR perhaps was due to the growth of NOB, probably fostered by the low
291 concentration of FA inside the reactor due to the low operating temperature, which decreased at 14.9°C
292 after 38 days of operation. Under these conditions, the FA levels inside the reactor at the beginning of the
293 cycle were found to be slightly lower than 2 mg NH₃/L, that could apparently be enough for NOB inhibition
294 (0.1-1 mg NH₃/L [16]). However, Shao et al. [30], reported inhibition of NOB activity by *Nitrospira* only at FA
295 levels between 1.83-9.61 mg NH₃-N/L. This indicated that since FA decreased throughout the cycle, the
296 inhibiting conditions for NOB metabolism were no more present, justifying the observed nitrate
297 accumulation. On the other hand, as reported by Salehizadeh and Van Loosdrecht [31], the rate of PHB
298 degradation in the famine phase is independent from the type electron acceptor, meaning that either
299 oxygen, nitrite or nitrate are suitable for the anabolic biomass metabolism under famine conditions. In any
300 case, mass balances showed that the daily amount of produced NO_x-N would have not been enough for the
301 S-SBR demand (1.2-1.5 kgNO_x-N/d). In addition, assuming that enough nitrates would have been produced,
302 a higher amount of carbon source for complete PHA-driven denitrification in the selection stage would

303 have been required. Indeed, the targeted COD/N for nitrite denitritation was set at 2.5 $\text{gCOD}_{\text{VFA}}/\text{gNO}_2\text{-N}$
304 [16], but this value would have been 40% higher considering COD requirements for nitrate reduction [29].
305 This would result in a reduction of substrate availability for PHAs production in the following accumulation
306 step if no external carbon source addition would be considered in real WWTPs. The best performances
307 were observed in period 2 and 3 due to the higher amount of produced nitrite (1.31 and 1.35 $\text{kg NO}_2\text{-N/d}$ as
308 average value), according to a vNLR of 1.64-1.72 $\text{kgN/m}^3\text{ d}$ and a NAR of 98.5 and 99.2% respectively. The
309 higher nitrite productivity was attributed to the higher operational temperatures of the N-SBR and the
310 increase of the SRT from 15 to 22-25 days. On one hand, this behavior seems to be in contrast with other
311 literature studies, where the application of SRT lower than 5 days was shown to enhance AOB selection and
312 NOB washout in synthetic municipal wastewater [32]. On the other hand, Jubany et al. [33] reported that
313 complete via-nitrite pathway was achieved in a three aerobic reactors system connected in series treating
314 extremely high strength (3000-4000 $\text{mg NH}_4\text{-N/L}$) synthetic wastewater operating with an SRT of 30 days. In
315 this case, the key parameters for NOB washout was found to be a right combination of FA levels, low DO
316 concentrations (1.2-1.9 $\text{mg O}_2\text{/L}$) and temperature (25°C). Considering the very similar operating conditions
317 of N-SBR, it was clear that a stable via-nitrite pathway was more suitable in period 2 and 3, respectively.
318 The different operational conditions of the N-SBR reflected the effluent characteristics. Indeed, the nitrite
319 concentration showed an average value of 111, 946 and 857 $\text{mg NO}_2\text{-N/L}$, while the nitrate concentration
320 was 207, 13 and 7 $\text{mg NO}_3\text{-N/L}$ for period 1, 2 and 3 respectively.

321 At the same time, different AUR value were observed due to the different operating conditions. As
322 reported in Table 6, during the first period, the AUR showed an average value of 22.3 mg N/L h , with a
323 specific AUR (at 20°C) of 16.2 mg N/g VSS h . The latter was slightly higher than the one reported for period
324 2 (14.3 mg N/g VSS h), probably due to the lower presence of residual biodegradable COD in the anaerobic
325 reject water (e.g. VFAs), which is a suitable well-known substrate for the growth of heterotrophic bacteria.
326 However, it is important to underline that the observed AUR in period 2 was equal to 55.7 mg N/L h , almost
327 three times higher compared to the previous period. Considering a similar daily aeration time for all the
328 monitoring campaign (21.4 h/d on average), the more favorable operating conditions in period 2 (e.g.

329 controlled temperature) resulted in a most consistent mass of ammonia effectively converted to nitrite
 330 every day. In the last period, the observed AUR was very similar compared to period 2, but the sAUR (at
 331 20°C) was 70% higher with an observed value of 22.5 mg N/g VSS h. This was due to the increase in the
 332 stability of the AD process with consequent decrease in soluble COD in the anaerobic supernatant, which
 333 resulted in a lower biomass concentration inside the reactor in period 3.

334 Table 6. Kinetics of AUR in the different periods (average and standard deviation were calculated within
 335 days 10-47 for period 1, days 200-319 for period 2 and days 407-613 for period 3).

Parameter	Unit	Period 1	Period 2	Period 3
		Average ±st.dev	Average ±st.dev	Average ±st.dev
AUR _{obs}	mgN/l h	21.6±3.4	55.7±6.2	56.4±5.8
sAUR	mgN/gVSS h	15.9±3.1	15.4±4.2	25.6±3.4
sAUR (20°C)	mgN/gVSS h	15.7±2.9	13.2±4.1	22.5±3.3

336

337 3.2 Performances of the S-SBR

338 The S-SBR was started up after the achievement of pseudo steady-state conditions in the N-SBR (day 17), to
 339 ensure an adequate amount of electron acceptor for a proper PHA-biomass selection. The feast/famine and
 340 aerobic/anoxic trends among the different experimental periods were reported in Figure 2 (a,b,c).

(a) ■ Period 1 ■ Period 2 ■ Period 3

341

(b) ■ Period 1 ■ Period 2 ■ Period 3

342

(c) ■ Period 1 ■ Period 2 ■ Period 3

343

344 Figure 2 a). Feast to famine ratio; b) Taerobic/Tanoxic ratio; c) TFeast/Taerobic ratio

345 After the start-up in period 1, the feast to famine ratio decreased from about 0.15 min/min to around 0.09
 346 min/min in 10 days. However, the $T_{\text{feast}}/T_{\text{aerobic}}$ ratio decreased from around 1 min/min to the minimum
 347 value of 0.11 min/min after 47 days. This was due to the extension of the aeration time, caused by the lack
 348 of electron acceptor provided by the N-SBR during the first experimental period. Indeed, the applied $v\text{NO}_2^-$ -
 349 NLR was only 0.05 kg $\text{NO}_2^-/\text{m}^3 \text{ d}$ while the $v\text{NO}_x$ -NLR was 0.14 kg $\text{NO}_x/\text{m}^3 \text{ d}$. Considering the latter value,

350 it is clear that it was quite lower compared with the potential capacity of the system, justifying the need of
 351 an aerobic phase duration extension. In this way, after the depletion of VFAs at the end of feast phase,
 352 aerobic famine conditions were established within the reactor for the remaining aeration time ($T_{\text{aerobic}} -$
 353 T_{feast}). This resulted in an increase of the $T_{\text{aerobic}}/T_{\text{anoxic}}$ ratio up to 0.92 min/min (Figure 2 b), indicating that
 354 anoxic famine conditions accounted only for about 44% of the total cycle length.

355 In periods 2 and 3 instead, the feast/famine ratio showed a quite constant average value of 0.09 min/min
 356 after the start-up (Figure 2 a). The operating conditions of the S-SBR were similar in both periods and
 357 resulted in an average $T_{\text{feast}}/T_{\text{aerobic}}$ ratio of 0.65 and 0.73 min/min in period 2 and 3, respectively (Figure 2
 358 c). Although these values could still appear low, it must be noticed that the length of the aerobic feast
 359 phase of the cycle was set on the changes in the DO profiles, due to the decreased oxygen consumption
 360 rate during the famine phase as reported by Wang et al. [34]. Taking into account the variability of the
 361 carbon source characteristics, it was decided to extend the aerobic phase of 10-15 min after the increase of
 362 DO concentration, in order to avoid residual VFAs concentration at the beginning of the anoxic famine
 363 phase. However, in period 2 and 3, the $T_{\text{aerobic}}/T_{\text{anoxic}}$ ratio decreased to 0.15 and 0.13 min/min respectively,
 364 resulting in a famine phase effectively accomplished for more than 94% under anoxic conditions (Table 7).
 365 The $v\text{NO}_x\text{-NLR}$ was efficiently increased up to 0.74 and 0.71 kg $\text{NO}_x\text{-N}/\text{m}^3 \text{ d}$ in period 2 and 3, however
 366 showing an average value of 0.47 and 0.49 kg $\text{NO}_2\text{-N}/\text{m}^3 \text{ d}$, respectively.

367 Table 7. Summary of feast/famine ratio and distribution among the different periods

Parameter	Unit	Period 1	Period 2	Period 3
		Average. $\pm$ st.dev	Average. $\pm$ st.dev	Average. $\pm$ st.dev
T feast	min/cycle	55 $\pm$ 19	47 $\pm$ 14	44 $\pm$ 19
T famine	min/cycle	527 $\pm$ 146	543 $\pm$ 142	484 $\pm$ 74
Feast/famine	min/min	0.10 $\pm$ 0.01	0.09 $\pm$ 0.02	0.09 $\pm$ 0.03
T feast/ t_{aerobic}	min/min	0.39 $\pm$ 0.24	0.65 $\pm$ 0.17	0.73 $\pm$ 0.07
T aerobic/ T_{anoxic}	min/min	0.52 $\pm$ 0.13	0.15 $\pm$ 0.04	0.13 $\pm$ 0.07
Aerobic famine/total famine	%	31.6 $\pm$ 9.7	5.3 $\pm$ 1.9	3.7 $\pm$ 1.4
Anoxic famine/total famine	%	68.4 $\pm$ 11.6	94.7 $\pm$ 1.8	96.3 $\pm$ 1.5

368

370

371 Figure 3. Substrate uptake rate and X_a concentration among the periods

372 The substrate uptake rate has been calculated during the whole monitoring period, since it was strictly
 373 connected with the feast to famine ratio. As shown in figure 3, the $-q_{VFA}$ increased from 60-100 mg COD/g
 374 X_a h up to 419, 477 and 485 mg COD/g X_a in period 1, 2 and 3, respectively. It is widely reported that PHA
 375 producers take advantage from their high velocity in substrate consumption over conventional
 376 heterotrophic growers [35]. Thus, it was clear that the selection strategy within the process was successful.
 377 In fact, the average $-q_{VFA}$ was quite similar all over the periods with a value of 301, 322 and 289 mg COD/g
 378 X_a h for period 1, 2 and 3, respectively. These results are higher with the one observed by Frison et al. [16]
 379 in a lab scale SBR, mainly due the higher SRT applied (12-15 day) which resulted in an average $-q_{VFA}$ of 239
 380 mg COD/g X_a h operating under aerobic-feast and anoxic-famine conditions. However, after day 500
 381 (period 3) a slight increase in the biomass concentration in concomitance with a simultaneous decrease in
 382 the substrate uptake rate was observed (Figure 3). This behavior was attributed to the increase of the non-
 383 VFAs and biodegradable fraction of the soluble COD in the carbon source, which is known to foster the
 384 growth of non PHA-accumulating biomass [12]. The average X_a concentration in the first period was equal
 385 to 1.4 g X_a /L, which decreased to 0.49 g X_a /L on day 82. This reduction was due to the lower biological
 386 activity consequently to the drop of the operating temperature up to 11°C, resulting in a lower substrate

387 uptake rate and subsequent growth of biomass. On the other hand, in period 2 and 3, the average biomass
 388 concentration was recovered up to 2 g Xa/L and 2.5 g Xa/L, due to more suitable operating conditions.
 389 Indeed, the temperature increase in combination with the higher nitrite availability, favored the effective
 390 PHA-biomass growth under strictly aerobic-feast and anoxic-famine conditions. The $Y_{\text{PHA/VFA}}$ under feast
 391 conditions was higher than 0.70 g COD_{PHA}/g COD_{VFA} in both period 1 and 2, while was lower in period 3, as
 392 shown in the table below (Table 8).

393 Table 8. Substrate uptake rate, PHA and growth yields in the different periods

Parameter	Unit	Period 1*	Period 2	Period 3
		Average± st.dev	Average± st.dev	Average± st.dev
$-q_{\text{VFA}}^{\text{feast}}$	mgCOD _{VFA} /gXa h	301±38	322±42	289±36
$q_{\text{PHA}}^{\text{feast}}$	mgPHA/gXa h	221±32	231±44	184±21
F/M	gCOD _{VFA} /gXa d	0.55±0.04	0.57±0.06	0.49±0.04
Y_{obs}	gXa/gCOD _{VFA}	0.29±0.02	0.29±0.01	0.31±0.02
$Y_{\text{PHA/VFA}}^{\text{feast}}$	gCOD _{PHA} /gCOD _{VFA}	0.74±0.04	0.72±0.04	0.64±0.16

394 * Considering only first 38 days of operation

395 The lower $Y_{\text{PHA/VFA}}$ in period 3 was attributed to the growth of non-storing PHA biomass able to consume the
 396 biodegradable non-VFA fraction of COD as carbon source. However, comparing the $Y_{\text{PHA}}^{\text{feast}}$ with the studies of
 397 Valentino et al. [12,36], which operated a pilot-scale SBR for PHA production from fermented feedstock
 398 with comparable COD_{VFA}/COD_{SOL} ratio under aerobic dynamic feeding (ADF), it seemed that the
 399 accomplishment of aerobic-feast and anoxic-famine conditions translated into a higher selective pressure,
 400 increasing the PHA yields under feast conditions. On the other hand, this behavior could have been a
 401 consequence to the fact that the applied vOLR in this study (0.7-1.5 kg COD/m³ d) could determine a “low-
 402 OLR enrichment strategy”, according with the conditions described by Albuquerque et al. [37]. Indeed, the
 403 same study reported a higher storage response over growth under vOLR lower than 2.5 kg COD/m³ day in
 404 an SBR operating under ADF with fermented molasses as carbon source. In addition, Korkakaki et al. [38]
 405 reported PHA yields up to 0.84 g COD_{PHA}/g COD_{VFA} under feast conditions in an SBR enriched under carbon-
 406 limiting conditions (vOLR <1.5 kg COD/m³ day). These results can highlight the fundamental role that this

407 parameter, in combination with the novel (aerobic)-feast/(anoxic)-famine, could have played in the PHA-
408 biomass selection strategy of the present study.

409 As regard as the F/M, the S-SBR operated under similar value during both period 1 and 2, while decreased
410 slightly in period 3 were an average value of 0.49 g COD_{VFA}/g X_a d was observed. On the other hand, the Y_{obs}
411 of the PHA-biomass ranged from 0.29 to 0.31 g X_a/g COD_{VFA} (Table 8). Considering the SRT applied in the
412 present study, these values were in agreement with the theoretical yields based on data reported in Henze
413 et al. [39] of 0.31 g X_a/g COD_{VFA}. However, despite the similar Y_{obs} observed during the whole monitoring
414 period, supposing a certain PHA content (e.g. 35-40% w/w), the lower biomass amount for the
415 accumulation step in period 1 due to the lower applied vOLR would have reduced the potential PHA
416 productivity of the system, thus limiting the overall process performances.

417

418 3.3 Performances of the via-nitrite nitrogen removal

419 Taking into account the Y_{PHA/VFA} under feast conditions and the NAR, the applied COD_{VFA}/NO_x-N ratio
420 threshold was calculated to ensure an average denitrification efficiency of around 85%.

421 The low NO_x availability in the first period resulted in an average applied vOLR of 0.77 kg COD_{VFA}/m³ d,
422 corresponding to a COD_{VFA}/NO_x-N ratio of 5.51 g COD_{VFA}/g NO_x-N. In both period 2 and 3, instead, the
423 average vOLR was increased at 1.15 and 1.22 kg COD_{VFA}/m³ d and the COD_{VFA}/NO_x-N was 2.41 and 2.49
424 gCOD_{VFA}/g NO_x-N, respectively (Figure 3). The higher COD_{VFA}/NO_x-N ratio in period 1 was consequence of
425 the over extension of the aerobic phase, where some intracellular PHA was supposed to be consumed for
426 biomass growth under aerobic conditions, instead of anoxic ones.

427 The targeted denitrification efficiency was not fully reached in period 1 (74.5 %), while was successfully
428 achieved in both periods 2 and 3 where an average efficiency of 87.7 and 86.0% was respectively observed
429 (Figure 4). Despite the similar efficiencies, the low NO_x-N loading rate of period 1 resulted in a low mass of
430 removed nitrogen (~0.34 kg N/d), compared to period 2 and 3, where around 1.1-1.2 kg N/d were
431 efficiently removed. However, if a higher denitrification efficiency should be required, it has been calculated
432 that a COD_{VFA}/NO_x-N ratio of 2.8-2.9 should be applied to the system if the NAR in the N-SBR is higher than

433 95%. This value is only 20-25% higher than the amount of the carbon source required for conventional
 434 denitrification ($2.2\text{-}2.3 \text{ g COD}_{\text{VFA}}/\text{gNO}_2\text{-N}$ [40]), highlighting the technology potential for carbon valorization
 435 through integrated PHA production and nitrogen removal.

436

437 Figure 4. COD/NO_x-N ratio and denitrification efficiency

438 A slight decrease in the denitrification efficiency was observed in the middle of period 3 (from day 500). This
 439 behavior was found to be in concomitance with the decrease in the substrate uptake rate as well as a small
 440 reduction in the $\text{COD}_{\text{VFA}}/\text{NO}_x\text{-N}$ ratio. These phenomena were probably connected, supporting the
 441 hypothesis that the presence of some non-VFA COD in the carbon source favored the growth of non PHA-
 442 biomass, thus reducing the carbon availability for via-PHA nitrite denitrification. Specifically, although the
 443 $\text{COD}_{\text{VFA}}/\text{NO}_x\text{-N}$ ratio was almost similar in period 2 and 3, the $\text{COD}_{\text{sol}}/\text{NO}_x\text{-N}$ ratio was 16% higher in period
 444 3. The overall nitrogen removal efficiencies under steady-state conditions (periods 2 and 3) were 79.9 and
 445 77.5%, respectively, when the applied nitrite loading rate was equal to 0.47 and $0.49 \text{ kg NO}_2\text{-N}/\text{m}^3 \text{ d}$. These
 446 performances were slightly better compared to the work of Frison et al. [16] where a nitrogen removal
 447 efficiency of 79% was found using sludge fermentation liquid as carbon source, but with an applied total
 448 vNLR of $0.42 \text{ kg NO}_2\text{-N}/\text{m}^3 \text{ d}$.

449

450 3.4 Cycle profile during PHA biomass selection

451 Several operating cycles were analyzed throughout the whole monitoring period to assess the process
452 performances. Nitrite, ammonium, VFAs, X_a , PHA and DO profile for a typical cycle of the S-SBR operating
453 during period 2 are reported in Figure 5.

454

455

456 Figure 5. Cycle profile of S-SBR

457 At the beginning of the (aerobic) feast phase, after the addition of the fermentation liquid, the VFAs
458 concentrations increased up to around 650 mg COD/L. The profile of the DO concentration showed an
459 increase up to 2.5-3.0 mg O₂/L when the aeration started and a suddenly decreased after about 4-5
460 minutes and stabilized at 0.8 - 1.0 mg O₂/L for around 45-50 min. This behavior was a consequence of the
461 increased metabolic activity [41], resulting in a VFAs depletion that took place with a rate of around 377 mg
462 COD_{VFA}/g X_a h. At the same time, PHA was accumulated within the biomass with a yield of about 0.71 g
463 COD_{PHA}/g COD_{VFA}, resulting in a PHA concentration of 10% (VSS basis) and 463 mg COD_{PHA}/L, respectively. As
464 soon as almost all the VFAs were consumed within 50 min, the DO concentration started to increase as a

465 response to substrate consumption [14], indicating that the feast phase was about to end. However, the
466 slow DO increase after the consumption of VFAs (from 50 to 70 mins) indicated the presence of some
467 slowly biodegradable COD in the carbon source [11]. After 70 minutes, anoxic famine conditions were
468 established by means of nitrite feeding, resulting in an initial concentration of 149 mg NO₂-N/L and an
469 exchange volume of around 0.14 m³/m³ reactor. Nitrites were completely depleted after 380 minutes of
470 famine phase, with a denitritation rate (at 20°C) of 11.4 mg NO₂-N/g X_a h. The PHA consumption efficiency
471 was > 94%, indicating that the internally stored carbon was effectively used as electron donor for nitrite
472 denitritation, resulting in a PHA content (VSS basis) equal to 0.3% at the end of the cycle. At the same time,
473 the ammonium concentration decreased from 153 to 139 mg NH₄-N/L in relation to the growth of PHA
474 storing bacteria [16].

475

476 3.5 PHA accumulation

477 The first accumulation tests were performed using acetate (COD:N:P = 100:0:0) as a reference carbon
478 source, since it is more favorable for the production of PHAs [42]. With this substrate, the biomass was able
479 to accumulate up to 49% of PHA (VSS basis) with a Y_{PHA} of 0.62 g COD_{PHA}/g COD_{VFA}. Although this value is
480 quite higher compared to other literature studies, it is in agreement with Valentino et al. [12], which
481 reported a Y_{PHA} during accumulation tests carried out with acetate of 0.67 g COD_{PHA}/g COD_{VFA}. The growth
482 yield ranged from 0.11-0.16 g X_a/g COD_{VFA}, indicating that a fraction of the substrate was consumed for cell
483 synthesis. This behavior was also reported by Frison et al. [16] and was attributed to the presence of N and
484 P in the liquor withdrawn from the S-SBR that was used as inoculum for the accumulation tests. The
485 produced biopolymer was composed by 100% 3-HB, in agreement with the results reported by Morgan-
486 Sagastume et al. [14]. After acetic acid, PHA production was evaluated without nutrients limitation using
487 real CPSFL (COD:N:P ~ 100:2:0.75) as a carbon source (Figure 6).

488

489 Figure 6. MLVSS, Xa, and PHA profiles of a typical accumulation test with CPSFL as carbon source

490 In this case, the PHA concentration (VSS basis) increased up to 42% after almost 4 h and then stabilized.

491 However, after that point, only the mass of both PHA and Xa increased, indicating a shift of carbon

492 utilization towards the synthesis of new biomass cells, as reported by Valentino et al. [43]. The same

493 authors found that under no nutrient limitation, the biomass growth during accumulation tests had

494 benefits on the final PHA production, since it increased the process' productivity. Similar results were

495 reported also by Jia et al. [44], where PHA accumulations were performed under nutrient abundance

496 (COD/N=10). The concentration of PHA in the biomass above 40% wt, (Table 9) has a significant impact on

497 further downstream recovery, as it is considered the threshold for the application of economical PHA

498 extraction processes [45]. The Y_{PHA} of the accumulation tests with CPSFL were on average 0.61 and 0.58 g

499 $COD_{PHA}/g COD_{VFA}$ in period 2 and 3, respectively, while the growth yield fluctuated from 0.18 to 0.24 g Xa/g

500 COD_{VFA} . The PHA yields observed in this study were higher in comparison with other studies, where PHA

501 production was investigated at pilot scale using fermented feedstocks as carbon source. PHA yields varied

502 between 0.25 and 0.51 g $COD_{PHA}/g COD_{VFA}$ (Table 9). On the other hand, the pilot-scale results of this study

503 underline the strength of this process in terms of PHA production and integrated via-nitrite nitrogen

504 removal from reject water.

505 Table 9. Comparison between different studies using fermented feedstocks for PHA production

Type of CS	$C_3/(C_2+C_3)$ (mol/mol)	%PHA (gPHA/gVSS x100)	$Y_{PHA/VFA}$ (gCOD/gCOD)	$Y_{X/VFA}$ (gCOD/gCOD)	PHA produced (kg/batch)	PHA productivity (mgPHA/L h)	HB:HV (% w/w)	Reference
Acetate (Period 2)	-	46.8±5	0.60±0.06	0.18±0.03	0.88±0.16	269±34	100:0	This study
Acetate	-	40±0.02	0.67±0.05	0.08±0.01	-	200±4	100:0	[12]
CPSFL (Period 2)	0.52±0.06	44.1±6	0.61±0.07	0.28±0.06	0.96±0.10	224±47	74:21-41	This study
CPSFL (Period 3)	0.49±0.08	39.6±2	0.58±0.05	0.32±0.05	0.85±0.05	234±37	76:24-40	This study
OFMSW+WAS FL	0.15-0.17	43-46	0.44-0.50	0.21-0.22	-	290-360	90:10-13	[12]
MWW+WASFL	0.24±0.04	27-38	0.25-0.37	0.22-0.32	-	108-151*	72:28-34	[14]
Primary sludge FL	0.24-0.26	38-45	0.31-0.51	-	-	-	72:28-45	[45]
Mixed I and II sludge FL	0.34*	19±2	0.40±0.04	0.23±0.06	-	-	56:42**	[16]
Mixed I and II sludge FL	0.29 ⁴	65.5	-	-	-	-	52:48	[42]

506 * Calculated considering the data provided by the authors

507 ** 2% Hydroxyhexanoate

508 The use of fermentative VFAs as carbon source affected the characteristics of the recovered biopolymer in
509 terms of HB:HV ratio. In this study, the HB content ranged from 59 to 76%, while the HV was found to be
510 between 21 and 41%. Comparing the present results with the work of Frison et al. [16], despite the ratio
511 between even and odd VFAs in the carbon source was quite high (0.34 and 0.49-0.52 mol/mol,
512 respectively), in both cases the HV content was comparable to polymers obtained from carbon sources with
513 lower amount of odd VFAs (Table 6). Carvalho et al. [46] investigated the effects of mixed microbial culture
514 (MMC) composition on PHAs production using fermented molasses as carbon source. The authors reported
515 that the polymer characteristics (e.g. % HB:HV content) were strongly affected by the operating conditions

516 (e.g. OLR and F/F ratio) which influenced the microbial community of the MMC. Low OLRs in combination
517 with low F/F ratio (i.e.<0.2 min/min) were found to be favorable for the growth of microorganisms able to
518 synthesize lower fractions of HV. This behavior was attributed by the tendency to operate decarboxylation
519 of propionyl-CoA to acetyl-CoA from these bacteria, as previously reported by Pardelha et al. [47], thus
520 reducing the final HV content. Another parameter that could have affected the polymer composition
521 observed in the present study could have been the pH value in the accumulation phase. Indeed, Kourmenza
522 et al. [48] investigated the effect of pH on PHA composition and the results showed that higher initial pH
523 (e.g.>7.5) led to lower HV production. These findings are in agreement with the present study, since pH in
524 the accumulation step ranged from 8.0 to 9.5. However, the same authors underlined again the impact that
525 both microbial consortia and operational conditions have on the characteristics of the biopolymer, making
526 somehow difficult the comparison of the results obtained in the present study with other works due to the
527 application of a non-conventional feast/famine process.

528

529 3.6 Assessment of the PHAs production potential and economic impact

530 For better understanding the impact of the PHA integration in the sidestream treatment line, an overall
531 mass balance was accomplished considering the AD of CPS and WAS as reference scenario. The complete
532 description and calculation behind the results shown in Figure 7 (a and b) were reported in the
533 supplementary information. In the reference scenario (Figure 7 a), the CH₄ production recovered from the
534 anaerobic digestion of CPS and secondary sludge was as high as 4.9 m³CH₄/PE y, corresponding to an
535 overall recovery of 0.32 gCOD per g of COD treated in the municipal WWTPs. The latter is slightly higher
536 than the value reported by Morgan-Sagastume et al. [15], due to the higher biodegradability of the CPS.
537 However, this value is still in the range reported by Tchobanoglous et al. [29], where the maximum amount
538 of recoverable COD was reported to be around 0.35 gCOD per gram of influent COD. In the second scenario
539 (Figure 7 b), the integration of PHAs production with nitrogen removal in the sidestream showed a
540 potential CH₄ recovery up to 4.0 m³CH₄/PE y. On the other hand, around 2.9-3.7 kg COD/PE y were

541 recovered as PHA biomass, equal to 20-25% of the total recovered COD. The COD fraction as PHA
 542 accounted up to 17.5% of the recovered COD, resulting in a potential production of 1.0-1.2 kgPHA/PE y. In
 543 agreement with Morgan-Sagastume et al. [15], the conversion yields of the influent COD into by-products
 544 was similar in both scenarios regardless if only AD or integrated PHA production was accomplished.

a

545

546

547 Figure 7. a) Reference scenario; b) AD and integrated PHA production scenario

548 In the reference scenario, the only revenues come from the biogas production (Table 10). Considering a CH₄
 549 market price of 0.12 €/m³ (0.04€/kgCOD_{CH₄} [49]), the recovered COD would be valorized as high as of
 550 0.58€/PE per year. On the other hand, although CH₄ production is slightly lower when AD is integrated with
 551 PHA production, the impact on the total profit is almost negligible. Indeed, since the market price of PHA
 552 ranges from 2 to 5 €/kgPHA [7,8,50], COD conversion into PHAs could be valorized from 30 to 70 times
 553 more in respect to CH₄. When PHAs production is integrated with AD, the global revenue would range from
 554 2.8 to 6.5 €/PE y, up to 11 times higher than reference scenario. Considering that the COD fraction of
 555 recovered PHAs represents only 11-18% of the total recovered COD, it appears immediately clear that the
 556 implementation of a sidestream technology able to integrate nitrogen removal and PHA production can
 557 significantly increase WWTP revenue.

558 Table 10. Comparison between recovered COD as biogas and PHA with related income for the different
 559 scenarios

Scenario	AD only		AD & integrated PHA production	
	kgCOD/PE y	€/PE y	kgCOD/PE y	€/PE y

Biogas	13.0-14.0	0.54-0.58	9.9-10.9	0.41-0.45
PHA biomass	-	-	2.9-3.6	-
PHA	-	-	1.7-2.1	2.2-5.9
COD recovered/Revenue	13.0-14.0	0.54-0.58	12.8-14.6	2.8-6.5

560

561 **4. Conclusions**

562 The upgrade of existing wastewater treatment plant aiming the resource recovery starts from the on-site
563 production of VFAs through acidogenic fermentation, which are the suitable carbon source for both energy-
564 efficient nutrients removal and PHAs production. Specifically, the present study evaluated both the
565 feasibility and the potential of PHAs production and nitrogen removal from the sidestream of WWTPs at
566 pilot scale. The results showed that around 80% of the influent ammonia was efficiently removed by the
567 system when both the N-SBR and S-SBR operated under $vNLR$ of 1.64-1.72 kgN/m^3d and 0.60-0.63
568 kgN/m^3d . Meanwhile, PHA-biomass selection was successfully accomplished by means of aerobic-feast and
569 anoxic-famine regime, as shown by the good PHA yields observed in the accumulation batches (0.58-0.61
570 $gCOD_{PHA}/gCOD_{VFA}$). The overall mass balance assessment pointed that up to 0.32 $gCOD$ per gram of COD
571 treated can be recovered as bio-based product (i.e. CH_4 , PHA, or both), regardless of the reference
572 scenario. If only AD is accomplished up to 4.9 m^3CH_4/PE per year can be produced, resulting in a final
573 revenue of 0.58 €/PE y. On the other hand, the integration of AD with PHAs recovery in the sludge line can
574 boost the revenues up to 11 times more with a final income up to 6.5 €/PE y. The PHA production potential
575 assessed in this study demonstrated that up to 1.2 $kgPHA/PE$ y can be produced when treating the sole
576 municipal wastewater. The application of an aerobic-feast and anoxic-famine regime can decrease energy
577 requirements for PHAs production due to its integration with the via-nitrite nitrogen removal from the
578 anaerobic reject water.

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***Declaration of Interest Statement**

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: